

Paper 20

IMPLEMENTATION OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN SAMSUNG – A CASE STUDY

Sangeetha Prabhu¹, & Krishna Prasad K.²¹Research Scholar, College of Computer Science and Information Science, Srinivas University, Mangalore, India²College of Computer Science and Information Science, Srinivas University, Mangalore, IndiaE-mail: sangeethaprabhu96@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

The worldwide search of artificial intelligence (AI) problems is in a fever pitch and the stakes are high. For several users, AI software is predicted to quickly become a lifestyle through daily conversations with a voice assistant or a customized IT, providing solutions focused on the auditory, sensory or emotional signals of a client. Samsung is now in a great position to turn the future of linked AI technologies to existence, from a wide variety of electronic products to 5G hardware to strong chipsets, centred on approximately half the billion products sold each year by the group. Samsung works with a vision that says "We must dedicate our human knowledge and technology to developing superior products and services, thus contributing to a greater global community." seeking to be a global leader that develops alongside people and local communities. Samsung is an international corporate South Korean technology company centered in Samsung City, Seoul. This is the biggest South-Korean multinational and consisting of various subsidiaries, most of whom under Samsung's name. In 1938 Samsung was formed as a trading firm by Lee Byung-Chul. The company expanded into the sectors of food production, fabrics, banking, bonds and distribution in the next three decades. In 1960s and in the mid-1970s, Samsung reached the electronics and constructing industries; these sectors would lead to further growth. In this paper, we made an attempt to analyze various AI technologies that the company provides, highlight their technical backgrounds and list out their applications, financial strategies, business challenges and products from Samsung.

Keywords: Samsung, Artificial Intelligence, Technology, IT industry, Electronics.

1. INTRODUCTION

From the time of its establishment as a tiny manufacturing firm in Taegu, Korea, Samsung was obviously one of the leading companies worldwide for computerized equipment, electronics and semiconductors, storage and the integration of frameworks. The innovative and high-quality Samsung services and processes are now viewed worldwide. Founded in 1938 in South Korea, Samsung has evolved in terms of approximately \$100 billion annual sales from a small trading firm to a multinational corporation in 1997[1]. Across three global industries-electronics, technology and chemicals-Samsung is working and employing workers in more than 60 cities. Corporate strategy is to dedicate the human knowledge and technology by increasingly better services and products to the creation of a modern society. As far as Samsung's brand is concerned, Samsung's confidence is focused on how it has done in recent years across all Samsung devices. Problems have been negligible with the products.

Yet Samsung has gained a status symbol for its consumers with its mobile phones. Samsung's service is also established and people know Samsung has a very quick service for any of its goods. So the product offering is now one of Samsung's greatest strengths in the Samsung advertising combination

2. AIMS AND OBJECTIVES OF STUDY

This is an undertaking case study report based on data obtained from the Samsung business models in the area of innovation of artificial intelligence[2]. The report discusses following aims and goals:

- Read among Samsung's biggest global IT firms ' service rates and business plans.
- To learn about Samsung's growth story line.
- Learn about the strategy of Samsung to confront challenges with Artificial Intelligence Technology
- STEEP and SWOT analysis used to suggest Samsung's potential performance plans.

3. JOURNEY OF SUCCESS

Samsung is a relatively newcomer to the very competitive wireless communication environment that develops a mobile telecommunications network in the late 1990s[2]. Samsung has now opted to use its GSM (Global System for Mobile Communications) networks for foreign markets with a foothold in CDMA's (such as USA and Korea). Samsung also introduced a brand building project in order to extend the company's brand to include products as part of the globalization movement in the field of technology.

4. FINANCIAL STATEMENT

A comparative summary of Samsung's Financials for last five years 2014 to 2018 is given in table 1 [3-9] and graphically represented in figure 1.

Table 1: Last five years Financial Statement

Income Statement	2018	2017	2016	2015	2014
Revenue	243.8	239.6	201.9	200.7	206.2
Gross profit	111.4	110.3	81.6	77.2	77.9
Operating profit	58.9	53.6	29.2	26.4	25.0
Profit before income tax	61.2	56.2	30.7	26.0	27.9
Net profit	44.3	42.2	22.7	19.1	23.4
Revenue by Segment					
SEMI	86.3	74.3	51.2	47.6	39.7
DP	32.5	34.5	26.9	27.5	25.7
IM	100.7	106.7	100.3	103.6	111.8
CE	42.1	44.6	44.7	44.8	50.2
Harman	8.8	7.1	N/A	N/A	N/A
Operating profit by Segment					
SEMI	44.6	35.2	13.6	12.8	8.8

DP	2.6	5.4	2.2	2.3	0.7
IM	10.2	11.8	10.8	10.1	14.6
CE	2.0	1.8	2.9	1.4	1.2
Harman	0.2	0.1	N/A	N/A	N/A
Operating margin by Segment					
Total	24.2	22.4	14.5	13.2	12.1
SEMI	51.7	47.4	26.6	26.9	22.1
DP	8.1	15.7	8.3	8.4	2.6
IM	10.1	11.1	10.8	9.8	13.0
CE	4.8	3.7	5.6	2.7	2.4
Harman	1.8	0.8	N/A	N/A	N/A
Regional portion of Revenue					
Domestic	14	13	10	10	10
America	34	34	34	34	33
Europe	18	19	19	19	21
Asia/Africa	17	18	19	21	20
China	18	16	18	15	16

Income Statement

Figure 1: Samsung's financial statement

5. ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE TECHNOLOGY IN SAMSUNG

5.1 On-Device Artificial Intelligence Technology

Samsung also extended the patented design of NPU software in the last year and even revised it. The firm also launched the optimized AI on-device framework for Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition (CVPR), and now Samsung has revised the optimized algorithm.

Samsung has revealed that its On-Device AI light weight technique has been successfully launched that conducts complex calculations 8 times higher than the current 32-bit deep server training dataset[4-6]. A key feature of the AI software on the computer is the capacity to calculate heavy-speed data in large quantities without electricity consumption.

Figure 2: On device AI Technology Network compression

The software defines the sequences of reliable data that affect ultimate deep learning output by learning, and it was said that Samsung Advanced Institute of Technology (SAIT) has conducted research that have shown effectively how the quantization of the in-server deep learning method at 32-bit cycles given greater accuracy than many other existing technologies when measured in less than 4 bits levels. The computation outcomes using the QIL method will produce similar results as existing applications when using 1/40 to 1/120 less transistors while deep learning information are provided in bit clusters of less than 4 bits. The 'AND' and 'OR' gates are permitted in contrast to arithmetical calculations[5]. AI software on smart phones will reduce the costs of cloud infrastructure for AI activities as it runs alone and delivers good and reliable results for applications like augmented reality and autonomous vehicles.

5.2 Bixby: Samsung's AI Assistant[5]

Bixby, a Samsungs Artificial Intelligence interface, has been launched to promote mobile interaction in the Samsung Galaxy S8 device. Bixby 2.0 includes an AI interface that can be installed with all TVs, refrigerators, notebooks as well as other wired computer devices. The latest version 2.0 promises to be a "easy leap forward to online help" and users can also link frequently with various other products and services. Bixby becomes comfortable with the human language and allows people to interact with increasingly complicated programs. Samsung intends to rival Google Home and Amazon Alexa with a Bixby assistant. The second-generation Bixby model was revealed by Samsung in 2017. Bixby 2.0 seems to be a "bottom line for electronic assistants" and "a daring reinterpretation of the platform." as per the company. Bixby 2.0 was planned to provide Bixby on All phones. Bixby 2.0 is open so designers can integrate the digital assistant into their applications and select how they interact with their applications. As for the smart phones Bixby can be used with both Galaxy S8 & S8+, Galaxy S9 & S9+ as well as with Galaxy Note 8. Across various items from TVs to household appliances, Samsung plans to expand the AI assistant. For starters, in January 2019

Samsung introduced a new frontload washing machine (model WF6300R) powered by Bixby. Samsung also has a Galaxy Home Bixby speaker. We've long anticipated several other firms to launch Bixby-powered stereo headsets, but comparable to Microsoft's Cortana, that is yet to arise. Alexa & Google Assistant have the smart speaker spot right now.

5.3 Samsung will add Artificial Intelligence to every device[6]

Samsung also confirmed at CES 2018 that perhaps the abilities of artificial intelligence will be part of each and every product created by 2020. This integrates these smart services onto a new Smart Things application to simplify access and monitoring of all phones, as result of this plan. All Samsung devices will not only be available for Internet of Things, but will have AI by 2020. AI & machine learning seem to be key strategic initiatives of Samsung.

5.4 AI technology based on machine learning to upscale images

The first one to announce 8 K AI software for televisions was Samsung Electronics. The software will automatically process content and improve minimum-resolution images to 8K picture quality[6]. With the introduction of high-resolution material on super high resolution display the breakthrough addresses the present problem. All images can now be changed to 8 K, which is the highest digital TV resolution today.

5.5 Samsung's AI robot

A new innovation from Samsung Electronics is Saram, a humanoid robot now being built with AI[7]. Samsung used the AI robotic arm technology in its own facility so far, but experts expect the company to market the robots even though it has still been completed. Sources confirmed that the vertical approach of Samsung's walking robot helps Saram to balance and cross multiple surfaces. Given advances in other robotic companies and the fact that robotics is a long-term research project for Samsung, Samsung seems to be quite timely at releasing its industrial robot. With its popularity and performance with iOS, devices and home appliances and previous AI experiences and an aggressive commitment to AI development and excellence, for Samsungs look promising to close that gap between themselves and rivals in the quest to ready themselves for the fourth industrialisation, including big data technologies, artificial intelligence & robotics.

6 SWOT ANALYSIS

Samsung Electronics Corporation Limited is the Samsung Corporation, a company headquartered in Suwon, South Korea, primarily a consumer electronics branch. Samsung is primarily known in and around Korea as the world's biggest mobile phone and laptop maker, including the widely successful and popular Galaxy. It is the largest TV and LCD panel producer in the world. Samsung is recognized as the second biggest consumer electronics throughout the world to its production and sales experience. SWOT Analysis seems to be an useful method to recognize your strengths and limitations and to recognize the opportunities that are open to you and the allegations that you face. What makes SWOT to be particularly strong is that it can help you exploit chances with thought. And you can manage threats that would otherwise make you unaware of the reality by understanding the limitations of your company[8]. Then you and your competitors will start developing a method that allows you

to vary from your competitors so you can compete successfully in your industry when it comes to looking about yourself and your competitors with the SWOT model.

6.4 STRENGTHS [8-9]

- Samsung is the world's most famous electronics manufacturer. It is also the world's leading TV, LCD, phone, and laptop manufacturer.
- Samsung was the world's number one smartphone marketing company in the second quarter of 2015 with a growing market share of 21.4 million.
- Apple has the number 2 in Samsung with 13.9 million with excellent design and production capabilities.
- Samsung Pay was enabled, in less than a year, to design and develop an Apple Pay payment platform with the same features.
- The functionalities of both the Apple Inc. and the Android device OS from Google Inc. are replicated by Samsung.
- Samsung has good production and distribution abilities.
- Samsung is very capable of producing and selling.
- Samsung has long-term collaborations with US and European companies which provide a sustainable channel for brands.

6.5 WEAKNESSES[8-9]

- Samsung could not suit the digital advertising capacity of Apple Inc. Between 2014 to 2015, U.S. mobile industry share fell by 2.3 million. At the other hand, Apple's share price increased by 34.9 percent.
- Many Chinese competitors are trying to keep up to Samsung on a mobile market. The share of Huawei increased by 48.1% during 2014-15, and the share of Xiaomi by 29.4%.
- Samsung relies heavily on exports of commercial products in markets with substantial growth potential, such as the U.S. & Europe, for much of its profits.
- Samsung's phones use Google Android's open source operating system.
- Obviously many consumers view Android as a costly Apple iOS product IOS has not been welcomed as much by the technology industry by the government as it has.
- Some consumers believe that Apple products are more advanced and much more consistent than Samsung brands.
- Samsung's marketing strategies are not as sophisticated as Apple's.

6.6 OPPORTUNITIES[8-9]

- The growing industry for smartphones, tablets and other portable devices, particularly in the growth of cell phones, tablets, and other devices industries, particularly in emerging areas, including Africa & India, where buyers are not satisfied with PCs.
- In 2015, tablet sales gradually surpassed traditional computer purchases.
- Increased demand for cellphone & tablet applications such as Samsung Pay New wearable devices.
- In the developing world, the rise of the middle class will boost the market for consumer products.
- The online market will grow from outlets such as Amazon

6.7 THREATS[8-9]

- In certain markets, including the United States, Apple has begun to emerge as the dominant phone and tablet brand. Samsung isn't in a role to overcome the business reputation of Apple.
- It appears that Apple is committed to consistency, quality and complexity.
- Galaxy smart phones depend on Google's Android OS, which is not as popular to ordinary people as iOS.
- Declining or diminishing middle-class incomes in both North America & United States that limit consumer purchasing power in all big Samsung markets.
- Chinese producers such as Xiaomi & Huawei can emerge as the major rivals of Samsung. When Samsung fell, the profitability of these industries has improved.
- Apple can enter adjacent consumer product markets such as household appliances, cameras and deal directly with Samsung in those industries.

7 CONCLUSION

Competitiveness of the global market for businesses demands Samsung to become more creative, not just in products and services of the firm, as well as in their tactics and approaches. Obviously, the success of Samsung allowed the company to return to becoming innovative inside the company. This engagement in senior management models by empowering staff to contribute and be active is successful and creative. Samsung discovered that their creativity rests primarily in the organization's citizens. Samsung seeing them as a most important asset. Because the workers were respected in the workforce, they feel a sense of satisfaction in what they did to help the company prosper. In all aspects of business, Samsung strives to aspire to become the world leader across communications and electronics. It involves education and providing incentives for the staff.

REFERENCES

- [1] History of Samsung Retrieved from <https://www.samsung.com/in/aboutsamsung/company/history/> on 09/12/2019.
- [2] Technological Advancement at Samsung Retrieved from <https://www.totalbusinessmagazine.com/2018/12/a-new-era-of-technological-advancement-at-samsung/> on 10/12/2019
- [3] Samsung's financial statement Retrieved from <https://www.samsung.com/global/ir/financial-information/financial-valuation-snapshot/> on 09/12/2019
- [4] Essays, UK. (November 2018). Technology And Innovation At Samsung. Retrieved from <https://www.ukessays.com/essays/marketing/strategic-technology-and-innovation-at-samsung-electronics-marketing-essay.php?vref=1> on 09/12/2019.
- [5] On device AI technology at Samsung Retrieved from <https://analyticsindiamag.com/samsung-creates-on-device-lightweight-ai-technology-that-is-8-times-faster/> on 09/12/2019
- [6] Samsung On-Device AI technology for AI Deep Learning Retrieved from <https://www.fonearena.com/blog/286030/samsung-on-device-ai-technology-for-ai-deep-learning.html> on 08/12/2019
- [7] The Amazing Ways Samsung Is Using Big Data and Artificial Intelligence Retrieved from <https://bernardmarr.com/default.asp?contentID=1504> on 09/12/2019

-
- [8] Jamali, M., & Khan, R. (2018). The impact of consumer interaction on social media on brand awareness and purchase intention! Case study of Samsung. *Journal of Marketing*, 114.
- [9] Chang, V., Zhang, W., & Xiong, C. (2019). The strategic view and development of corporate social responsibility: the case study of Samsung. *International Journal of Strategic Decision Sciences (IJSDS)*, 10(1), 105-130.
- [10] Kang, C. K. (1997). Ownership structure of Samsung chaebol. *Beyond the firm: Business groups in international and historical perspective*, ed. T. Shiba, and M. Shimotani, 31-58.
- [11] Magnusson, P., Westjohn, S. A., & Zdravkovic, S. (2011). "What? I thought Samsung was Japanese": accurate or not, perceived country of origin matters. *International Marketing Review*, 28(5), 454-472.
- [12] Leachman, R. C., Kang, J., & Lin, V. (2002). SLIM: Short cycle time and low inventory in manufacturing at Samsung Electronics. *Interfaces*, 32(1), 61-77.
- [13] Baloh, P., Uthicke, K., & Moon, G. (2008). A business process-oriented method of KM solution design: A case study of Samsung Electronics. *International Journal of Information Management*, 28(5), 433-437.
- [14] Moro, S., Pires, G., Rita, P., & Cortez, P. (2018). A cross-cultural case study of consumers' communications about a new technological product. *Journal of Business Research*.
- [15] Chen, S., Li, Z., Dangelo, F., Gao, C., & Fu, X. (2018, March). A Case Study of Security and Privacy Threats from Augmented Reality (AR). In *2018 International Conference on Computing, Networking and Communications (ICNC)* (pp. 442-446). IEEE.
- [16] Lee, Y. W. (2019). Enhancing shared value and sustainability practices of global firms: The case of Samsung electronics. *Strategic Change*, 28(2), 139-145.
- [17] de MARTINI, A. L. E. S. S. A. N. D. R. O. (2018). The role of design thinking in exploring the opportunities embedded in interaction technologies. Case study about Samsung Design Center.
- [18] Wilson, N., & Makmud, S. T. (2019). THE IMPACT OF BRAND EVALUATION, SATISFACTION, AND TRUST TO BRAND LOYALTY: A CASE STUDY OF THE INDONESIAN SMARTPHONE INDUSTRY. *Jurnal Muara Ilmu Sosial, Humaniora, dan Seni*, 2(2), 633-649.
- [19] Lu, H., Li, Y., Chen, M., Kim, H., & Serikawa, S. (2018). Brain intelligence: go beyond artificial intelligence. *Mobile Networks and Applications*, 23(2), 368-375.
- [20] Almutairi, M., Mehta, S., Al Rashidi, F., Villa, M. A., & Anggawinata, F. (2019). Analysis of Samsung's internationalization process and the strategies implemented to generate an effective positioning of its brand and products in foreign markets. *Journal of the community development in Asia*, 2(1).
- [21] Lee, H. B., & Chung, T. Y. (2018). A Comparative Analysis on Page Caching Strategies Affecting Energy Consumption in the NAND Flash Translation Layer. *IEMEK Journal of Embedded Systems and Applications*, 13(3), 109-116.
- [22] Kim, S. K. (2018, December). Developing the Strategies for AI Products based on the Technology Decomposition Framework. In *2018 IEEE International Conference on Industrial Engineering and Engineering Management (IEEM)* (pp. 1250-1254). IEEE.